

Research Article

A Cross-Sectional Study To Assess The Knowledge, Attitude And Practice Of Cosmetic Use Among Different Individuals In Bangalore

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ABSTRACT

As per schedule Y (Drugs and Cosmetics act 1940: Amended in 2016), cosmetics are defined as “articles intended to be rubbed, poured, sprinkled, or sprayed on, introduced into, or otherwise applied to the human body or any part thereof for cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness, or altering the appearance” [1]. It includes any article intended for use as a component of cosmetics. This study aimed to assess the awareness of safety, knowledge about the ingredients used, the criteria for choosing cosmetics and the possibilities of side effects caused by using cosmetics in different individuals. The study was questionnaire-based wherein google forms were prepared and circulated among people. Sample size was 500 with participants ranging from below 18 years to above 50 years. Out of 500 participants, the response rate was 60.4%. Only 23.84% of the participants belonged to the male category. Many of the participants (50.9%) preferred skincare over beautification cosmetics. 21.62% chose cosmetics based on the quality. About 90% were aware of the harmful ingredients in cosmetics. 35% were aware of the adverse effects of cosmetics. Only 37.09% were aware that all cosmetic products are approved by the central authorities before reaching the market. 20.16% had the habit of reading labels before usage. The use of cosmetics is very prevalent in the present generation but the adverse effects of it are less familiar. To establish safe and effective usage of cosmetics, consumers need to stay informed and develop appropriate habits to prevent complications.

INTRODUCTION

Cosmetics are the products one can apply on the body (e.g., skin, nails, body hair, hair, lips, genitalia, teeth, and mouth) to clean the given area,

improve one's smell and appearance, and keep oneself in good condition include personal care, hair care, oral care, makeup, and nail care products

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as well as moisturizers, fragrances, depilatories, and sunscreens[2].Cosmetic is defined under section 3 of the Drugs and Cosmetics Act, 1940 as, any article intended to be rubbed, poured, sprinkled or sprayed on, or introduced into, or otherwise applied to, the human body or any part thereof for cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness or altering the appearance, and includes any article intended for use as a component of cosmetic. Nowadays, cosmetic is one of the elements that bring attractiveness to human. It is becoming a trend for most people especially women and teenager to use cosmetic in their daily life [3]. Cosmetics have not only seeped into the fashion world but are also playing a prominent role in one’s day-to-day life. Thus, it becomes a necessity to make people aware of the various harmful effects of cosmetics and chemicals used in cosmetics [4]. People in the age group of 18-35 years are more inclined towards the use of cosmetics. Females and that too students hold the major chunk of this group. Frequency of using cosmetics has also increased with a greater number of people now using cosmetics daily. Most people now believe that expensive products are better than cheaper ones. The same goes with the use of herbal products with people willing to spend more on them. Cosmetic products contain a wide range of chemicals to which we are exposed every day[5]. For a customer different factor can govern

the decision to buy a particular cosmetic, such as the brand with which the product is associated, quality and price of the product, location of the place from where the product is to be bought, quality of the packaging and advertisements and promotions that have been employed to publicize the product in the market. The main significance of cosmetics is to instill a new decent look to the person after application. Even though there is a booming success in cosmetic industry, the actual meaning of cosmetics is misunderstood in many Western countries as mere makeup products.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The cross-sectional study is questionnaire-based conducted by approaching different individuals within a specified area by the Department of Pharmaceutics. The sectional study was conducted by recruiting 500 people in Bangalore especially in south part of Bangalore by asking more than 15 questions.

RESULTS

Out of 500 people 302 people submitted the filled forms of the questionnaire. Hence the response rate was 60.4%. The results were as follows.

GENDER DISTRIBUTION OF STUDY PARTICIPANTS

Many of the participants were females (230,76.16%) followed by males (72, 23.84%) as shown in the figure 1.

RESULTS		
Options	%	Count
Male	23.84	72
Female	76.16	230
Others	0.00	0

Figure 1; Gender wise distribution of the study population

AGE DISRIBUTION OF STUDY PARTICIPANTS

Most of the participants between age 18-25 (240 ,79.47%) and above 50 only 6 people responded. Figure 2.

RESULTS		
Options	%	Count
Below 18	5.63	17
18-25	79.47	240
26-35	7.28	22
36-50	5.63	17
Above 50	1.99	6

Figure 2; age-wise distribution of the study population

OCCUPATION-WISE DISTRIBUTION OF THE STUDY POPULATION

In the study most of the participants were students (75.8%) and 19.2% people are working in different professions.as shown in the figure 3.

Figure 3; occupation wise distribution of study population.

AWARENESS ON DIFFERENT COSMETIC PRODUCTS

Most of the people are familiar and use shampoos (65.9%) and hair oils (59.6%). figure 4.

Figure 4; Usage Of Several Types Of Cosmetics.

BUYING OF COSMETICS BY THE PARTICIPANTS.

products frequently and 9.3% of participants never buy cosmetic products means may be not using any kind of cosmetics as shown in figure 5.

38.7% of participants buy cosmetic products rarely. 36.1% of participants buy cosmetic

RESULTS		
Options	%	Count
Rarely	38.74	117
Frequently	36.09	109
Very frequently	15.89	48
Never bought	9.27	28

How often do you buy cosmetic products?

302 responses

Figure 5; buying of the cosmetics by the participants.

PARTICIPANTS PURPOSE FOR USING COSMETICS

PURPOSE FOR USING

Most of the participants use cosmetics for protection (21.37%) and beautification (17.04) as shown in figure 6.

RESULTS		
Options	%	Count
Beautification	17.04	122
To boost self esteem	10.61	78
For protection	21.37	153
Prescription by physicians	9.50	68
To minimize aging	8.52	61
For cleansing purpose	17.88	128
To conceal imperfections	7.26	52
Other	7.82	56

What is your purpose of using cosmetics (select all that apply)

302 responses

Figure 6; purpose of using cosmetics.

AWARENESS OF INGREDIENTS USED IN COSMETICS

The majority of people know that water (172) and talc (108) are used in preparation of cosmetics. figure 7.

Figure 7; Awareness On Ingredients Used In Cosmetics.

AWARENESS ON HARMFUL INGREDIENTS OF COSMETICS

The majority of the participants were aware of all the substances as harmful ingredients followed by lead

(12.92%), parabens (12.01%), sodium lauryl sulfate (11.10), benzophenone and formaldehyde (9.01), triclosan (8.36) as shown in figure 8.

Figure 8; Awareness On Harmful Ingredients Of Cosmetics.

AWARENESS OF ADULTERATED COSMETICS

53.97% of the participants are aware of adulterated cosmetics and 46.03% people don't know that cosmetics will be adulterated, figure 9.

RESULTS		
Options	%	Count
Yes	53.97	163
No	46.03	139

Figure 9; awareness on adulterated cosmetics

AWARE OF THAT ALL COSMETICS PRODUCTS ARE APPROVED BY THE CENTRAL AUTHORITIES

Only (37.09%) of people are aware that cosmetics products are approved by the central as shown in figure 10.

RESULTS		
Options	%	Count
Yes	37.09	112
No	32.12	97
Not sure	30.79	93

Are you aware that all cosmetic products are approved by the central authorities?
302 responses

Figure 10; aware of all cosmetics are approved by the central authorities.

FOLLOWING OF SPECIFIC DIRECTIONS WHILE USING COSMETICS.

Most of the people (45.7%) follow the directions that are written on the pack of the cosmetic products or in the manual. 25.2% of people follow the directions every time and 20.2% of people

follow the directions rarely and the most considering point is that 8.9% of people never follow the directions. Figure 11.

While using cosmetics, do you follow the specific directions of usage ?

302 responses

Figure 11; following of specific directions while using the cosmetics.

SELECTION OF COSMETICS BASED ON PARTICULAR SKIN TYPE.

59.3% of participants are choose cosmetic products based on their skin type. 23.8%

participants are not choosing based on their skin type. Figure 12.

RESULTS		
Options	%	Count
Yes	37.09	112
No	32.12	97
Not sure	30.79	93

Do you select cosmetics based on your particular skin type

302 responses

Figure 12; selection of cosmetic products based on their skin type.

PERCENTAGE OF COSMETIC PRODUCTS DERIVED FROM NATURAL SOURCES.

34.8% of people are saying that their cosmetic products are 50% derived from natural sources and 24.2% of people say that their cosmetic products

are more than 50% derived from natural sources.25.2% people say that they don't know that their cosmetic products are derived from natural sources or not. Figure 13.

RESULTS		
Options	%	Count
Yes	37.09	112
No	32.12	97
Not sure	30.79	93

How much percentage of your cosmetics are derived from natural sources?
302 responses

Figure 13; percentage of cosmetic products are derived from the natural sources.

EFFECTIVENESS OF COSMETICS AS ASSURED BY ADVERTISEMENTS.

Only 10.3% of participants are saying that their cosmetics are fully effective as assured by the advertisement. 40.4% of participants say that their

cosmetics are partially effective and 13.2% of participants say that their cosmetics are not effective at all as assured by the advertisements. Figure 14.

RESULTS		
Options	%	Count
Fully effective	10.26	31
Partially effective	40.40	122
Slightly effective	36.09	109
Not effective at all	13.25	40

Figure 14; effectiveness of cosmetics as assured by advertisements.

DISCARD OF COSMETIC PRODUCTS EVEN IF IT NOT EMPTY.

27.8% of people discard the cosmetic products on the date of expiry. 28.2% of people discard the

products after expiry date only and 23.2% of people are discard cosmetic products one month before expiry. Figure 15.

Figure 15; discard cosmetic products even if it is not empty.

FOLLOWING OF TIPS WHILE USING COSMETIC PRODUCTS.

Most people (62.3%) have a habit of keeping a container of cosmetics clean, 57.9% have a habit of reading the labels on packages of cosmetics and

most importantly discarding the products in case of their change in physical appearance, 58.6%.of people have a habit of washing their hands before using cosmetic products. Figure 16.

Figure16; following of tips while using cosmetic products.

KNOWLEDGE ON ADVERSE EFFECTS OF COSMETIC PRODUCTS.

28.5% of participants are known about the adverse effects of certain cosmetic products and 20.9% of

participants don't know about adverse effects knowledge and poor education of cosmetic caused by cosmetic products shows the less products. Figure 17.

RESULTS		
Options	%	Count
Yes	28.48	86
No	20.86	63
Little	35.10	106
Not sure	15.56	47

Do you know the adverse effects of your cosmetic products?

302 responses

Figure 17; knowledge on adverse effects of cosmetic products.

FACTORS INFLUENCE CHOICE OF COSMETIC PRODUCTS

Quality of the cosmetic products is more influence factor in choice of cosmetics, brand and price also

have the high influence on choice of cosmetic products. Figure 15.

Which factors influences your choice of cosmetics? (Select all that apply)

302 responses

Figure 18; facts influence on choice of cosmetic products

SIDE EFFECTS HAVE EXPERIENCED DURING OR AFTER USING PARTICULAR COSMETIC PRODUCTS

Majority of the people are suffered from the side effects of cosmetics in that most of them had pimples and acne (14.97%), and 12.88% suffered

from hair fall or dandruff, also some people got skin irritation while using cosmetic products (13.23%) as shown in the figure 19.

Figure 19; side effects have been experienced during or after using a cosmetic product.

CONCLUSION

Cosmeceuticals offer both challenges and rewards to patients and their physicians. As society holds a youthful and healthy appearance to be of utmost importance, many people feel anxious about their aging skin and seek physician advice on what to do [6]. Knowledge about cosmetic use was good among participants but the awareness regarding harmful effects and cosmetics are approved by the central authority was comparatively less. In the present scenario as cosmetics use is more prevalent, there is need to educate people about the risks of cosmetics. The usage of cosmetics has been increased to many folds in personal care system and there is great demand for cosmetics and also have a tremendous scope in cosmetic usage in upcoming year. Therefore, I conclude by saying that cosmetic plays a key role in day-to-day life and is used by every gender thereby, creating an increase in cosmetic usage and scope also has an important role.

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